

were complementary to the region of the P 194 open reading frame of the RTBV genome.

In PCR amplifications using wax beads (Ampliwax PCR Gem 100), the PCR reagents were mixed separately as lower and upper components. The lower reagent mix contained 1X PCR buffer (50 mM KCl, 10 mM Tris-HCl, pH 8.3), 0.2 mM of each dNTP, 2.5 mM of MgCl₂, and 0.5 μM of each of two primers, made up to a total volume of 25 μl per reaction tube using sterile deionized water. A wax bead was added in each reaction tube. The wax was melted by incubating the reaction tubes at 80 °C for 5 min. Melted wax was layered over the lower reagent mix. After wax layering, the reaction tubes were either used directly for PCR reactions or stored at 4 °C until needed. The upper reagent mix contained 1X PCR buffer, 2.5 units (0.5 μl) of *AmpliTaq* polymerase and 100 ng (15-25 μL) of total nucleic acid extract of insect tissue, made up to a total volume of 65 μL per reaction tube. Upper reagent mix was aliquot to each reaction tube above the solid wax layer, PCR amplifications were carried out for 45 cycles with a denaturation temperature of 94 °C for 1 min, annealing temperature of 53 °C for 2 min, extension temperature of 72 °C for 3 min, and a final extension temperature of 72 °C for 5 min. PCR products were examined with ethidium bromide-stained 2% agarose gel in 1X TBE buffer using size markers ranging from 100 to 1000 bp.

To obtain viruliferous insects, female adults of the four insect species reared on virus-free TN1 were exposed to RTD-infected TN1 rice plants for 3 d. Among 30 insects from each species tested, PCR detected RTBV in several individual insects of vector species such as *Nephotettix virescens*, *N. nigropictus*, and *Recilia dorsalis*, and in one nonvector species, *Nilaparvata lugens*. (Results of PCR on 10 individual insect samples from each species are shown in Figures 1 and 2.)

Amplification of RTBV DNA in the nonvector occurred presumably from RTBV particles that had entered the insect gut through ingestion of plant sap containing the virus. Absence of desired PCR products in some viruliferous insects may

be because of the presence of undigested enzyme inhibitors, variability in the amount of viral DNA in individual insects, or rapid viral nucleic acid degradation. PCR is an expensive technique, particularly if the reagents are not assembled in the lab and expensive kits must be purchased. As our results

show, the technique can be very sensitive, but that sensitivity does not necessarily indicate the identification of a vector. Further considering all these difficulties, we found that PCR is not a reliable virus detection method for the routine population analyses of viruliferous vectors of rice tungro. ■

Modified method of gel consistency test with small samples

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Gel consistency test is a reliable index for cooked rice texture. We modified Cagampang's method to develop a reliable method for small samples (10 mg). We analyzed the gel consistency of 10 varieties and two varieties with known gel consistencies—M. Sungsong (soft) and Basmati 370 (medium)—as controls.

The protocol for the modified gel consistency test is as follows: 1. Grind the samples into a fine powder (100 mesh). 2. Put a 10-mg sample of powder into a 10- × 75-mm test tube. Add two drops (0.02 ml) of 95% ethanol containing 0.025% thymol blue as an indicator. 3. Mix the contents well in a cyclo-mixer for 1 min. 4. Immediately add 0.2 ml of 0.2 N KOH and mix well again for 1 min in the mixer. 5. Cover the test tube with a glass marble and place it over a boiling water bath for 5 min. Contents should not exceed 2/3 the height of the tube. 6. Cool the test tube at room temperature for 6 min, and then transfer it to an ice water bath, maintaining a constant temperature of 8-9 °C for 5 min. 7. Lay the chilled test tube horizontally on a table for 30 min. 8. Measure length of the gel in mm from the bottom of the tube to the top of the gel. Gel is classified as hard (6-10 mm), medium (11-20 mm), and soft (more than 20 mm). Previously, time was not specified in steps 3 and 4, nor was specific temperature for the ice water bath.

The classification of rice based on gel length was modified according to the results of the controls. Nine of the 12 varieties had hard gel consistency; only Pakistan Basmati and Basmati 370 had

Gel type of 12 varieties tested.

Genotype	Gel length (mm)	Gel type
Sitabhog	10.3 ± 0.3	Hard
T412	10.0 ± 0.5	Hard
CR1009	10.0 ± 0.5	Hard
CR1018	9.67 ± 0.3	Hard
Ratna	9.67 ± 0.3	Hard
Karnal Local	9.67 ± 0.3	Hard
EC205265	9.67 ± 0.3	Hard
CR1014	9.67 ± 0.3	Hard
Tulasimanjari	9.33 ± 0.5	Hard
Basmati 370	11.66 ± 0.3	Medium
Pakistan Basmati	10.67 ± 0.3	Medium
M. Sungsong	31.0 ± 1.5	Soft

medium type (see table). Based on this analysis, the modified method is reliable and time-saving and will be useful when handling many varieties. ■

A simple method to assess the relative amount of leaf wetness in rice canopies

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Leaf wetness is a critical factor in the development of many diseases. Leaf wetness in the plant canopy may come from dew, guttation, rain, or irrigation. Leaf wetness in rice crops is influenced by canopy structure (leaf area, density, and angle), which is, in turn, affected by plant development stage and cropping practices, including planting density.

Leaf wetness measurement is possible using sophisticated — and often expensive — mechanical or electronic leaf wetness sensors or recorders. In many cases, several sensors must be used to address the vertical structure of the canopy and its successive layers. The

1. An assessment scale for rating leaf wetness in a plant canopy, where 0 = dry, 1 = with a few scattered big droplets, 2 = with a thin film of small droplets, and 3 = with a dense film of small droplets. Approximate weight (mg/cm^2) of water corresponding to each rating scale is 1 = 1.50, 2 = 2.50, and 3 = 4.50.

number of sensors is again increased when several treatments that affect the canopy structure are handled in a single experiment. Moreover, most sensors measure leaf wetness indirectly: wetness of artificial surfaces is actually recorded. These artificial surfaces may react differently from plant surfaces, leading to erroneous observations. We developed a

2. Leaf wetness rating and duration over time at different layers of the rice canopy at LAI = 3 (a), 7 (b), and 8 (c). Each point is the mean of 10 observations.

simple method to determine the amount of leaf wetness at different layers of the rice canopy.

The method is based on direct observation, with a four-point rating scale where 0 = dry; 1 = few, scattered big droplets; 2 = thin film of small droplets; and 3 = dense film of fine droplets (Fig. 1). The approximate amount of

water corresponding to each rating scale is indicated in Figure 1.

Assessments can be made at the upper layer, middle layer, and base of the rice canopy. The effect of leaf area index (LAI) on leaf wetness in three layers of a rice canopy is shown in Figure 2. Observations were made from 0600 to 1200 h. The average duration of leaf wetness increased as LAI increased. The upper layer of the canopy initially had the highest mean leaf wetness rating, which declined faster than that of the lower layers after 0800 h. The average leaf wetness duration of the middle layer was the longest.

This simple method was used in field experiments during the 1992-93 wet season and dry season using IR72 with the following N input levels as treatments: no fertilizer (N0), 80 kg N/ha (N1), and 120 kg N/ha (N2). During the cropping season, 10 leaf wetness assessments were made and taken on 10 hills in each N treatment at 0600 h. During the wet season, mean leaf wetness ratings were N0 = 1.38 b, N1 = 1.70 a, and N2 = 1.78 a (values followed by the same letter are not significantly different at $\text{LSD}_{0.05}$). During the dry season, means were N0 = 1.61 b, N1 = 2.11 a, and N2 = 2.38 a. These results showed that variation in canopy structure, which is affected by the amount of N fertilizer, caused differences in leaf wetness.

This method allows direct observations of leaf wetness in different layers of a canopy at desired frequency and interval. Although flexible, it is more time-consuming and difficult to use in determining the exact time of water deposition and disappearance than are leaf wetness sensors. This method is currently being used in understanding the relationship between leaf wetness and spread of sheath blight. ■